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Evaluation of Aeronet AOD at 1640 nm in scenarios with collocated instruments

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Abstract

The AOD at 870 nm, 1020 nm, and 1560 nm, was compared between three collocated instruments at PMOD/WRC, Davos, from September 2023 to September 2024. The measurements were used to assess the trace gas corrections used by AERONET to correct the AOD retrievals at the 1020 nm and 1560 nm channels. The trace gas correction at 1020 nm is due to absorption by water vapour and amounted to 0.003 and 0.006 for the AERONET calculations and the BTS measurements respectively. The trace gas corrections at 1640 nm are due to the combined absorptions by water vapour, carbon dioxide, and methane, and amounted to 0.013 for both AERONET calculations and BTS measurements. This confirms the trace gas corrections applied by AERONET at 1020 nm and 1640 nm with an estimated standard uncertainty of 0.003 at 1020 nm and 0.001 at 1640 nm.

Introduction

This deliverable investigates the Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) retrieved in the infrared spectral channels at 870 nm, 1020 nm, and 1640 nm using the BTS spectroradiometer system, a Precision Filter Radiometer (PFR), and a Cimel CE318 (AERONET). The measurements were performed at PMOD/WRC, Davos Switzerland, from September 2023 to September 2024. While the CIMEL and PFR are calibrated using the traditional Langley-based procedure and are traceable to their respective networks (AERONET and GAWPFR), the BTS spectroradiometer system is calibrated using SI-traceable transfer standards (Gröbner et al., 2023).

The advantage of the BTS is that a continuous AOD spectrum from 300 nm to 2150 nm is obtained, and therefore spectral regions unaffected by trace gases can be used, specifically the nearby spectral region at 1560 nm, close to the 1640 nm channel of the CIMEL radiometer. Using the 870 nm and 1560 nm AOD measurements, which are unaffected by trace gases, AOD values at 1020 nm and 1640 nm were obtained using a log-log (Angstroem) fit, which will be labelled BTSext, 1020ext and 1640ext in the respective figures.

The Angstroem coefficients obtained from the PFR channels at 368 nm, 412 nm, 500 nm, and 870 nm, were used to calculate the extrapolated AOD at 1020 nm, and 1640 nm. Due to this extrapolation, the AODs retrieved at 1020 nm and 1640 nm are unaffected from the trace gases present at these spectral channels. The uncertainty of this extrapolation has been investigated and is less than 0.005.

In this study, the trace gas corrections applied by the AERONET v.3 algorithm at the 1020 nm and 1640 nm channel are validated with regard to the PFR and BTS measurements. The trace gas corrections that were applied to the measurements of the 1020 and 1640 channels of the AERONET radiometer were directly obtained from the AERONET database for all individual measurements, and also compared to the published formulas (Gilles et al., 2019).

Without trying to develop a detailed uncertainty budget for the measurements used in this study, we assume on the basis of past studies published in the peer-reviewed literature, standard uncertainties of the AOD obtained from the three instruments of 0.01.

Results

Measurements at the 870 nm channel

The measurements at the 870 nm channel are used to assess the agreement of the three instruments at a spectral channel unaffected by trace gases. As seen in Figures 1 and 2, the agreement between all three instruments is excellent, with an average difference in AOD of 0.001 and a standard deviation of 0.004 over the investigated period.

Figure 1 Top: AOD at 870 nm from BTS, CIMEL (AERONET) and PFR, and bottom: differences in AOD relative to the CIMEL for the period covering September 2023 to September 2024.

Figure 2 Histograms of the differences in AOD shown in Figure 1 from BTS and PFR with respect to the CIMEL (AERONET). The thin lines represent a normal distribution fitted to the data (outliers were removed).

Measurements at the 1020 nm channel

The AOD measured at 1020 nm is available from BTS and CIMEL (AERONET), but not from the PFR. Figures 3 and 4 show the AOD uncorrected for trace gases, which at this particular channel is only due to water vapour. The average AOD difference between BTS and CIMEL is 0.006 with a standard deviation of 0.005, which is well within the combined uncertainties of the two instruments.

Figure 3 Top: AOD at 1020 nm from BTS and CIMEL (AERONET) and bottom: differences in AOD relative to the CIMEL for the period covering September 2023 to September 2024.

Figure 4 Histogram of the differences in AOD shown in Figure 3 from BTS to CIMEL (AERONET). The thin line represents a normal distribution fitted to the data (outliers were removed).

AOD corrected for trace gas absorptions at 1020 nm

Figures 5 and 6 show the AOD obtained at 1020 nm using trace gas corrected AOD from the CIMEL (AERONET), the extrapolated AOD from the PFR and the interpolated AOD from the BTS using nearby spectral regions unaffected by trace gases. As can be seen in the figures, the agreement is also excellent, with average AOD differences to the CIMEL of 0.003 and 0.006 for the BTS and PFR respectively.

Figure 5 Top: AOD at 1020 nm for BTS (interpolated), CIMEL (AERONET) and PFR (extrapolated), and bottom: differences in AOD relative to the CIMEL for the period covering September 2023 to September 2024.

Figure 6 Histograms of the differences in AOD shown in Figure 5 for BTS (interpolated), PFR (extrapolated) relative to the CIMEL (AERONET). The thin lines represent a normal distribution fitted to the data (outliers were removed).

The trace gas corrections at 1020 nm can be retrieved from the BTS measurements and compared to the calculated correction used by AERONET. According to AERONET, the optical depth τ of precipitable water vapour at 1020 nm is $\tau = 0.0020 \cdot IWV$ (cm). The trace gas correction is retrieved from the BTS measurements by subtracting the optical depth at 1020 from the interpolated AOD at 1020. Figure 7 shows the trace gas corrections from BTS and AERONET with respect to precipitable water vapour for the measured period at PMOD/WRC, along with the calculated trace gas correction using the formula from AERONET.

Figure 7 Trace gas correction for 1020 nm from measurements (BTS), and from calculations (AERONET) with respect to Integrated water vapour (IWV) in mm.

As can be seen in Figure 7, the trace gas correction calculated by AERONET is between 0.001 and 0.005 and clearly correlated to the precipitable water vapour (IWV) as expected from the formula. The optical depth difference from the BTS obtained from subtracting the AOD obtained from the interpolated AOD measurements at 1020 nm from the AOD measured directly at 1020 nm is more variable but has the same magnitude and dependence on IWV.

Figure 8 Histogram of trace gas corrections at 1020 nm as measured by BTS (left figure), and as calculated by AERONET (right figure).

The histograms shown in Figure 8 for the same data displayed in Figure 7 show that the average optical depth difference (= trace gas correction) is 0.006 and 0.003 for BTS (measured) and CIMEL (AERONET) (calculated) respectively. The small difference of 0.003 in the trace gas corrections obtained from BTS and AERONET is well within the measurement uncertainties of the BTS.

Measurements at the 1640 nm channel

The AOD measured at 1640 nm is available from BTS and CIMEL (AERONET), but not from the PFR. Figures 9 and 10 show the AOD uncorrected for trace gas absorptions, which at this particular channel are due to absorptions by water vapour, carbon dioxide and methane.

Figure 9 Top: AOD at 1640 nm from BTS and CIMEL (AERONET) and bottom: differences in AOD relative to the CIMEL for the period covering September 2023 to September 2024.

Figure 10 Histogram of the differences in AOD shown in Figure 9 from BTS to CIMEL (AERONET). The thin line represents a normal distribution fitted to the data (outliers were removed).

There is a slight offset in AOD between BTS and CIMEL, with the BTS measuring slightly higher AOD than CIMEL, with an average of +0.009. Even though this difference is within the combined uncertainties of both instruments, it points to a systematic error in either the BTS or CIMEL AOD retrieval at this wavelength. Additional measurements (not shown here) with an additional spectroradiometer traceable to the SI (QASUME-IR, see Gröbner et al., 2023), are in excellent agreement with the BTS at 1640 nm. This could indicate a systematic error in the atmospheric transmission at 1640 nm as retrieved from the SI-traceable measurements of BTS and QASUME-IR, which are both traceable to SI via the same transfer standards, and the Solar Spectrum TSIS-1 HSRB used as Top of the Atmosphere reference. As mentioned before, this discrepancy is currently within the measurement uncertainties and needs further work to clearly identify its origin.

AOD corrected for trace gas absorptions at 1640 nm

Figures 11 and 12 show the AOD obtained at 1640 nm using trace gas corrected AOD from the CIMEL (AERONET), the extrapolated AOD from the PFR and the extrapolated AOD from the BTS using spectral regions unaffected by trace gases (870 nm and 1560 nm).

Figure 11 Top: AOD at 1640 nm for BTS (extrapolated), CIMEL (AERONET) and PFR (extrapolated), and bottom: differences in AOD relative to the CIMEL for the period covering September 2023 to September 2024.

Figure 12 Histograms of the differences in AOD shown in Figure 11 for BTS (extrapolated), PFR (extrapolated) and CIMEL (AERONET). The thin lines represent a normal distribution fitted to the data (outliers were removed).

In contrast to the results at 870 nm and 1020 nm, the average AOD difference of 0.009 at 1640 nm between BTS and CIMEL (AERONET) is clearly higher than the AOD difference seen between PFR and CIMEL. This strengthens the hypothesis that the retrieval of AOD at 1640 nm from the BTS (and QASUME-IR) has an offset due an inconsistency between the SI-traceable irradiance measurements and the Top of the Atmosphere solar Spectrum TSIS-1 HSRS used to calculate the atmospheric transmission.

The trace gas optical depth calculations used by AERONET V3 are described in Giles et al., 2019. The optical depth from CO₂ and CH₄ absorption at 1640 nm, scaled with the pressure of 840 mb at Davos, amounts

to 0.0111, to which is added the optical depth of precipitable water vapour. The resulting optical depth trace gas correction τ is $\tau = 0.00111 + 0.0014 \cdot IWV(cm)$. Figure 13 shows the optical depth trace gas corrections at 1640 nm obtained from the BTS measurements using the same methodology as at 1020 nm and from AERONET.

Figure 13 Optical depth of trace gases at 1640 nm retrieved from BTS measurements (violet) and from AERONET (blue).

As can be seen in Figure 13, the agreement of the optical depth from trace gases at 1640 nm between the BTS (measurements), and AERONET (calculations) is excellent. Figure 14 shows the histograms, with an average trace gas optical depth from BTS of 0.013, in perfect agreement with those from AERONET (also 0.013). The uncertainty of this trace gas correction (defined as the standard deviation of the measurements of the BTS) is very small, 0.001.

Figure 14 Histogram of trace gas corrections at 1640 nm as measured by BTS (left figure), and as calculated by AERONET (right figure).

Figure 15 shows the trace gas corrections from BTS and AERONET with respect to precipitable water vapour for the measured period at PMOD/WRC, along with the calculated trace gas correction using the formula from AERONET.

Figure 15 Trace gas correction for 1640 nm from measurements (BTS), and from calculations (AERONET) with respect to Integrated water vapour (IWV) in mm.

As can be seen in Figure 15, the trace gas corrections calculated by AERONET are between 0.011 and 0.015 and clearly correlated to the precipitable water vapour (IWV) as expected from the formula. The optical depth difference from the BTS obtained from subtracting the AOD obtained from the extrapolated AOD measurements at 1640 nm from the AOD measured directly at 1640 nm is more variable and does not really show any correlation with IWV.

Furthermore, the average trace gas absorption due to water vapour, carbon dioxide, and methane of 0.013 is confirmed with independent measurements obtained from high spectral resolution measurements using a FTIR during a measurement campaign in 2022 (Gröbner et al., 2023).

References

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